

A Study on Consumer Behavior towards Durable Goods- with Special reference to Theni District

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Abstract

Consumer behavior is center of modern marketing, understanding his behavior is quite essential for efficient and effective marketing management. Customers may state their needs, wants but act otherwise. They may not be in touch with their deeper motivations. India's consumer market is riding the crest of the country's economic boom. Driven by a young population with access to disposable incomes and easy finance options, the consumer market has been throwing up staggering figures. Marketing problem enhancing from the consumer's behavior has a greater degree of similarity behavioral problems relating to the consumer durables. Use of durable goods is becoming increasingly popular in recent years in India. The introduction of different types of durables has also brought out many significant changes in the tastes and preferences of ultimate consumers in recent years.

Keywords: Consumer behavior, Durable goods, Non-durable Goods

Introduction

In India, there are various resources and people are more prone to use a variety of products for their consumption. The process of consumption in the post liberalized era has started dominating the consumer community. There are numerous products that available in the market for the consumption and this situation has created for consumers. The multiple products with similar utility have created a competitive situation in the market. People at one side are unable to decide what to buy, and on the other side, they remain faithful to some products in particular. Thus, consumer behavior is one of the significant areas to be studied. The globalization and liberalization operation of businesses have given an opportunity to the customers/ consumers to select one out of various similar products available in the market. The global trend in the market have affected the consumer's behavior to a great extent, whether it is a case of seller operating in international, regional, local level or a case of consumers involved in purchasing consumable/ industrial products. Due to the globalization of business and liberalized policies of the government, the auto industry has witnessed a major selling prospect. Many multinational companies has entered fray, turning the market place into a virtual battlefield.

Consumer

An individual who buys products or services for personal use and not for manufacture or resale. A consumer is someone who can decide whether or not to purchase an item at the store, and someone who can be influenced by marketing and advertisements. Any time someone goes to a store and purchases a toy, shirt, beverage, or anything else, they are making that decision as a consumer.

Consumer behavior -Meaning

Consumer behavior is a decision process and physical activity individuals engage in when evaluating, acquiring, using or disposing of goods and services. Consumer behavior reflects the totality of consumers' decisions with respect to the acquisition, concerning disposition of goods, services, time and ideas by (human) decision-making units.

Consumer behavior - Definition

The American Marketing Association (AMA) defines consumer behavior as “The dynamic interaction of cognition, behavior and environmental events by which human beings conduct the exchange aspect of their lives.”

Durable goods & Non-durable goods

Consumer goods are many times separated into two categories (i.e.) durables and non-durables.

Durable goods are a category of consumer products that do not need to be purchased frequently because they are made to last for a long time (usually lasting for three years or more). They are also called consumer durables or durables.

Consumer durable goods include automobiles, books, household goods (home appliances, consumer electronics, furniture, tools, etc.), sports equipment, jewelry, medical equipment, firearms, and toys.

Non-durable Goods are products consumers purchase with the plan to use for a short period. Also referred to as consumable goods, most non-durable goods are expected to be consumed or used in three years or less. Because of this basic characteristic, non-durable goods can be a wide variety of products.

Non-durable goods include fast-moving consumer goods such as cosmetics and cleaning products, food, condiments, fuel, beer, cigarettes and tobacco, medication, office supplies, packaging and containers, paper and paper products, personal products, rubber, plastics, textiles, clothing, and footwear.

Statement of the Problem

The marketers have to play a key role in attracting potential buyers in favor of their products. The buying decision varies as per the information available with the women consumer before buying a particular product. Information available through the Internet with the help of cable TV has created a new dimension in making a decision before buying any product. Thus, the decision of buyers depends a lot on the information available with the buyers. All the purchases made by a family follow a certain decision-making process.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the socio-economic profile of the selected respondents.
2. To identify the problem faced by the consumer while purchasing.

Methodology

The data for the purpose of the present study have been collected through primary and Secondary data.

- **Primary data** Primary data has been collected through a structured questionnaire from 100 respondents in Theni District.
- **Secondary data** Secondary data include published data such as data from Books, journals, periodicals, Reports, etc.

Analysis of Consumer Behavior

In Theni District there are 100 consumers were taken for this study by adopting convenient sampling method. The demographic factors of consumers include variables such as age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, type of family, number of members, monthly income and Problems while purchasing. It is presented in table 1.1.

Table 1: Personal Profile

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	%	
1	Age	Up to 20 years	50	50
		20-30 years	20	20
		Above 30 years	30	30
		Total	100	100
2	Gender	Male	20	20
		Female	80	80
		Total	100	100
3	Marital Status	Married	40	40
		Unmarried	60	60
		Total	100	100
4	Educational Qualification	Up to School level	20	20
		Graduation Level	60	60
		Diploma	20	20
		Total	100	100
5	Occupation	Student	30	30
		Employer	40	40
		Business	30	30
		Total	100	100
6	Type of Family	Joint family	80	80
		Nuclear family	20	20
		Total	100	100

7	Number of Members	Up to 3 members	20	20
		3-6 members	50	50
		6 and above	30	30
		Total	100	100
8	Monthly Income (Rs.)	Up to Rs.15000	20	20
		Rs.15001 - Rs. 20000	50	50
		Above Rs. 20000	30	30
		Total	100	100
9	Problems While Purchase	Non-availability of the expected products	10	10
		After sales service	28	28
		Lower quality of the products	30	30
		More time consumption	10	10
		Defective products	12	12
		Guarantee given by sellers	10	10
		Total	100	100

Sources: Primary data

Table 1.1 clearly explain the majority of the respondents (50%) are belonging to the age group up to 20 years, most of the consumers (80%) are female, majority of the consumers (60%) are unmarried, most of the consumers (60%) are under graduates. Majority of the women consumers (40%) are employed in both public and private sector, the majority of the consumers (80%) are in the joint family, most of the consumers (50%) family having 3-6 members and majority of the consumers (50%) monthly income between Rs.15001 – Rs.20000. Most of the consumers (30%) are given problem while purchasing only lower quality products.

Findings of the Study

The various findings of the study are given in the followings

- Majority of the respondents (50%) are belong to the age group up to 20 years,
- Most of the consumers (80 %) are female,
- Majority of the consumers (60%) are single,
- Most of the consumers (60%) are under graduates.
- Majority of the consumers (40%) are employed in both the public and private sector.
- Majority of the consumers (80%) are in the joint family.
- Most of the consumers (50%) family having 3-6 members and

- Majority of the consumers (50%) monthly income between Rs.15001 – Rs.20000.
- Most of the women consumers (30%) are given problem while purchasing only lower quality products.

Suggestions of the Study

Based on the findings of the study and the opinion expressed by the consumers the following suggestions are given:

- Since the product is widely available, the sellers must improve the quality of the products.
- Marketers should focus their efforts to increase the level of consumer satisfaction through initiating modifications in product related issues like price, design and brand image.
- Most of the women consumers buy for credit facilities arranged by the same dealers either in banking or private finance companies.
- The availability of credit facilities makes the buyers buy costly products and make them pay in installments conveniently.

Conclusion

This study concludes that the competitive market provides an opportunity on the one hand and threats on the other hand to both the consumer segment of women and products of the product. It is quite important to improve core product with value addition to enrich customer satisfaction more in similar price range. Not only quality improvements but improvement in after - sales service can develop and replace demand for consumer durables as well as for replacement of the products. The dealers / producers and the retailers must understand the importance of the consumers and their change attitude in the process of marketing. Only then the companies can withstand and survive in the sale of consumer durables.

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